

On the development of a research integration tool for inter- and transdisciplinary science

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Submission Type. software, project

BoK Concepts. DA, CV, GS

Keywords. Geospatial information, visualisation, inter- and transdisciplinary research, open source

1 Introduction

Inter- and transdisciplinary projects are increasingly demanded for tackling complex issues of societal relevance, such as climate adaptation, but these projects come with numerous challenges regarding integration (Lawrence et al., 2022; Pohl et al., 2021). We use experiences from a large inter- and transdisciplinary research unit in the climate and water sector, situated in the Berlin-Brandenburg region, where we identified the need for a common technical platform & visualization tool for heterogeneous data and information as crucial. Our aim is to develop a user-friendly tool that serves the following internal and external purposes:

- (1) Internally, support the identification of joint research questions, topical linkages, and data integration between disciplines.
- (2) Externally, provide interactive access to scientific results for transdisciplinary exchange within workshop formats.
- (3) As curated outreach platform, enable to communicate the interconnectedness and regional embedding of climate & water issues

Specifically, we aim to answer the following research question: How should a research integration platform be designed to adequately display interdisciplinary (qualitative and quantitative) spatial science?

1.1 Examples of existing platforms

Recent high-profile initiatives to establish digital twins, such as Destination Earth (<https://destination-earth.eu/>) attempt to raise access to geospatial data and insights to a new level. However, regional administrations still tend to produce data download hubs without much context information (“data over the wall” principle, Sieber and Johnson, 2015), like the Geoportal Brandenburg (<https://geoportal.brandenburg.de>) or the now deprecated FIS-Broker Berlin (<https://fbinter.stadt-berlin.de/fb>). The low flow information system within *Auskunftsplattform Wasser* (<https://apw.brandenburg.de/>) contextualizes hazard monitoring by background data, although with a less user-friendly interface, dominated by pop-ups. At *Klimafolgen online* (<https://www.pik-potsdam.de/de/produkte/klimafolgenonline>), quantitative climate model projections are made interactively accessible in a well-documented way. Indicators are presented in long lists within scrollable side bars. The Feral Atlas (<https://feralatlus.org/>) by Tsing et al. (2020) presents a creative approach from the anthropology

Figure 1. Schematic flowchart of our stepwise development process

domain, for thematically sorted qualitative material. A format suited for merging qualitative and quantitative map-based content is the StoryMap, which has been successfully tested for educational purpose (Cope et al., 2018).

2 Methods

Early in the project we approached the researchers involved in the project “Climate and Water under Change” (www.cliwac.de) – 28 research groups ranging from numerical climate modelers to anthropologists – collecting their requirements during major project retreats, incl. roundtable discussions and bilateral exchange (Fig. 1). Although conceptual guardrails were defined from this bottom-up initiative, the major part of implementation was conducted in rather agile fashion, repeatedly involving researchers from different fields to iteratively improve the concept. Due to the required flexibility, we decided for a fully custom backend / frontend setup. After an initial development phase, we are now engaging with potential users outside the research consortium in workshop settings to test the user experience and introduce further user-centric functionalities.

2.1 Data and Software Availability Section

Our tool is being developed under a permissive free and open source license, allowing sharing and adaptation of the code once published. The public release is planned for Q3/2025.

3 Results

3.1 Core concept

From the initial discussions among the interdisciplinary project consortium we distilled the following key aspects:

- (1) **Interdisciplinarity:** natural sciences and humanities are seen as complementary. Spatial representation of text-based research is needed, e.g. inspired by the StoryMap format.
- (2) **Interactivity:** Live model runs need to be possible, e.g. together with stakeholders during workshops.
- (3) **Collection of knowledge:** a platform to host (intermediate) results for improved internal & external communication – no raw data download.
- (4) **Curation:** contributions need descriptions and pre-sorted topical connections as approachable entry point.
- (5) **Exploration:** users should be able to combine topics outside the curated connections.
- (6) **Expandability:** an open technical framework should allow for external contributions, accelerate future development and reuse.

3.2 UI/UX and navigation elements

A navigation graph provides clear thematic structure and avoid the unfamiliar user to get overwhelmed (Fig. 2). When picking a topic, the user is presented a set of predefined related topics to explore and hold side by side on the map.

Figure 2. Development version of the navigation graph

On the map view, the side panel gives an immediate overview of active datasets and story markers (Fig. 3). The lower panel is used for rendering tools to control the dynamic or multi layered datasets as well as live models. It is also used to show brief summaries that expand on click.

Figure 3. Map view with right panel and lower panel in use, with example data.

The left panel displays in-depth information for rich media and text focused content, which allows for simultaneous exploration of locations or regions related to the content (Fig. 4). We strictly decided against popups to avoid clutter.

Figure 4. Left panel text related to location markers.

3.3 Software

The implementation is based on open source industry-standard libraries. The frontend is a React based Single Page Application written in typescript. It leverages Leaflet for the map visualization. The backend is a Python FastAPI server, backed by a PostGIS database and a storage for serving tile layers, static content and the configuration.

Discussion

The biggest challenges during developing the concept was to appeal both to the natural and social science user base and to acquire and manage different available data types, quality and characteristics. We therefore e.g. included a topic navigation in a thematic plane beside the classic map-based interface. The user evaluation and iterative refinement is still ongoing.

Python as the language of choice allows for embedding scientific codebases directly into the project. The flexible

UI structure works for a predefined set of data categories and configurations. A bottleneck for reusability appears to be the entry barrier for the onboarding of additional data. Prepared configuration sets aligned to documentation and validation functions lower this barrier.

To leverage the true potential of such tools for the inter- & transdisciplinary research process, the backbone would have to be available from an early project stage on. This is typically at odds with the realities of third-party funded research, limited to a few years, and rather requires a committed hosting institution with longer term funding to advance the framework in parallel to the individual research projects.

Conclusions

We started to develop an interactive platform to present research results from different disciplines as a coherent whole, and use the development process to drive thematic integration within an inter- and transdisciplinary project. With a mix of curation via graph-based thematic sorting and freedom for exploration on a map, our platform attempts to convince different types of users, while presenting quantitative insights embedded in rich qualitative context information. We continue to engage potential users from the water & climate sector. Our open source technical framework may be re-used and adapted in upcoming projects, where it could be available as flexible and expandable backbone.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have not used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript.

Acknowledgements.

We thank all project members of CliWaC contributing to this work, as well as the Berlin University Alliance and Einstein Foundation Berlin for funding (ERU-2020-609). Special thanks to TD-Lab for funding the continuation and workshops (CX24).

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